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Geminivirus and Plant Resistance in Molecular Perspective

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Abstract

Geminivirus is a broad spectrum phytopathogen with increasing severity and incidence in the last two decades. From a molecular perspective, this virus has 5 - 7 important proteins which function as a regulator of transport, transmission, replication, encapsulation and pathogenicity. The urgency of understanding the molecular mechanisms at which the virus infects is in determining which substances are involved in the penetration of the host cell. Understanding these mechanisms can assist in developing analytical strategies to increase plant resistance. A clear interaction is seen between geminivirus with several proteins involved in resistance and apoptosis and is classified into the Systemic Acquired Resistance (SAR) mechanism. This resistance system gives the plant the ability to respond to infection by various pathogens that attack it through substantive interactions that occur. Interactions can be analyzed in-vitro (EMSA, Yeast 2 Hybrid / Y2H etc.) and In-silico. The two editors support each other so as to produce a flow of molecular interactions of the proteins involved. This paper will explain about geminivirus and its interaction with SAR through a molecular perspective.

Keywords: *Geminivirus, Molecular Interaction, Systemic Acquired Resistance (SAR)*

Geminivirus

Geminivirus (Geminiviridae) is a broad spectrum destructive phytopathogen. This virus attack has become an epidemic that causes economic losses to the world agricultural sector (Fondong, 2013). The distribution of this virus from Africa and Asia has resulted in production failures such as: *Maize streak disease (MSD)*, *cassava mosaic disease*, and *cotton leaf curl disease* (Legg and Fauquet, 2004; Shepherd *et al.*, 2010).

Based on the agreement of the consortium and the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses, *Geminivirus* genome classification and virus vectors are grouped into seven plant virus genera, namely: *Begomovirus*, *Mastrevirus*, *Curtovirus*, *Becurtovirus*, *Eragovirus*, *Topocuvirus* and *Turncurtovirus* with genome composition in the form of single circular DNA packed into virions and replicative double strands. which was transcribed on the nuclei of the infected plants through the Rolling circle replication (RCR) mechanism (Rojas *et al.*, 2005) (Figure 1).

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Figure 1. Illustration of the genomes of the four genera *Geminivirus*. A. genomes *bipartite* DNA-A and DNA-B, B. Begomovirus, C. Mastrevirus, D. Curtovirus, E. Topocovirus. Source: (Fondong, 2013).

The components of the genome *Geminivirus* consist of one (monopartite) and (bipartite) which encodes 5 - 7 proteins involved in a number of functions including virus replication, particle transport, encapsidation, transmission, and pathogenicity (Hanley-Bowdoin *et al.*, 2013). Briddon and Stanley (2006) stated that the satellite DNA begomovirus encodes a protein that plays a role in increasing the level of viral pathogenicity.

infection symptoms *Geminivirus* seen in infected plants such as dwarf, yellowing and curly leaves. Furthermore, it causes the failure of normal development of the reproductive organs which is evidence of changes in the transcription orientation of the host. These changes lead to cell homeostasis and developmental processes. This evidence was confirmed by Naqvi *et al.* (2010) used a transcriptome profile of infected plants. The two identify gene expression from different processes, ranging from immunity, cell death programming to DNA replication and cell cycle regulation. This infection also causes loss of the host's miRNA regulatory system associated with plant hormonal signaling.

Geminiviruses can undergo rapid genetic makeup changes that are difficult to control. Mutations can be, recombination and a mixture of both which can increase the diversity of the virus. Navas-Castillo *et al.* (2011), explained that a resistant vector biotype is in line with the vector response to insecticides. This evolution causes the increased severity or distribution of the virus to new areas which leads to an increase in disease complexity. Although the interaction between *Geminivirus* and its vectors is still not well understood, recent research indicates a change in signal and defense pathways caused by infection *Geminivirus* (Hanley-Bowdoin *et al.*, 2013).

The virus that causes Curly jaundice in Chili (*Capsicum annum*) is known as Pepper Yellow Leaf Curl Virus (PepYLCV). Viruses belong to the family *Geminiviridae*, where the genome organization is classified as *monopartite* and *bipartite*. This grouping is based on the existence of genome A and genome B for *bipartite*. groups *Monopartite* Are characterized based on the existence of genomes such as DNA-A along with β -satellite components (Briddon *et al.*, 2008; Jamsari and Pedri, 2013). According to Xie *et al.* (2010) stated that genome A and genome B function in proliferation. In addition, Genome A is involved in protein replication, regulation of gene expression and protein coat formation; whereas the B genome includes proteins that are involved in the movement of viral particles (Briddon *et al.*, 2008). The β -satellite component of the DNA-A genome is involved in increased pathogenicity and symptom expression accompanied by the accumulation of *helper viruses* in infected plants.

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The role of NPR1 in SAR (*Systemic Acquired Resistance*)

Systemic Acquired Resistance (SAR) provides broad-spectrum resistance to pathogens such as bacteria, fungi, viruses, insects and other types of pathogens. This resistance is not only in the infected areas of the plant, but occurs as a whole or systemically. The accumulation of salicylic acid, or its analogues such as 2,6-dichloroisonicotinic (INA) and *benzothiadiazole* (BTH) is reported to be able to induce SAR (Fu and Dong, 2013). SAR is a manifestation of the action of *Effector Triggered Immunity* (ETI) and transaction triggered by *MAMP-Triggered Immunity* (MTI), an increase in salicylic acid concentration in cells, the activity of a number of signal cascades and the production of antimicrobials such as pathogen-related proteins (*Pathogen-Related Proteins*). Wang *et al.*, 2006).

Non-Expressor of Pathogen-Related Genes (NPR1) is a key regulation of SAR resistance mechanisms. Research on plants with the model *Arabidopsis thaliana*, salicylic acid gave a signal to the NPR1 resistance regulator center, also known as *Non-Inducible Immunity* (NIM1), *Salicylic Acid Insensitive 1* (SA1), or *Enhanced Disease Susceptibility 17* (EDS17). NPR1 is also a transcription regulator of many types of resistance genes that control a number of immune responses and plant health. Structurally, NPR1 is in the form of two conservative protein interaction domains, namely repeated Ankyrin domains and *Broad Complex Tramtrack and Bric-a`-Brac / Poxvirus and Zinc-Finger* (BTB / POZ).

Induced NPR1 showed an increase in Ca²⁺ in the cytoplasm due to infection from pathogens. The increase in Cation concentration 2 resulted in the release of the interaction between *Suppressor of NPR1 Inducible1* (SNI1) and *Calmodulin-Regulated NAC* (CBNAC) *Transcription Factor* and resulted in the of the *Suppressor of releaseSNI1 2* (SSN2) which previously interacted with CaM to be released. The SA concentration also influences the activity of the NPR1 protein. On the condition of normal cells, proteins NPR1 which has been transported into the nucleus of the cell does not undertake *binding* to SA so that it interacts with NIMIN(*Non-InducibleImmunity1(NIM1)-Interacting*) and protein X (a protein which is not yet known) that inhibit activation of the gene PR1 (Pajerowska-Mukhtar *et al.*, 2013).

The mechanism of the NPR1 gene activates the PR-1 gene starting with a change in the structure of the oligomeric NPR1 protein to become the monomer of the NPR1 protein (Lindermayr *et al.*, 2010), then with the help of *mobile proteins*, NPR1 can enter the cell nucleus (Fu and Dong, 2013). NPR1 in the cell nucleus forms a monomer that interacts with salicylic acid in the domain *Transactivation* (TA), which frees the bonds that occur between the TA and BTB / POZ domains. Liberation of the BTB / POZ domain causes the transcription factor TGA2 on the promoter side to bind to the BTB / POZ domain, thereby eliminating the function of *repressor* TGA2. After the transcription factor becomes active, new RNA polymerase can attach to the promoter side and read the PR-1 gene sequence (Wu *et al.*, 2012).

The NPR1 gene has been isolated from several plants such as *Arabidopsis* (Sandhu *et al.*, 2009), apples (Malnoy *et al.*, 2007), sugarcane (Chen *et al.*, 2012), cotton (Parkhi *et al.*, 2010), chili's (Villanueva-Alonzo *et al.*, 2013), and bananas (Zhao *et al.*, 2009). The increased expression of several NPR1 genes such as rice, tomatoes and wheat has shown the ability to resist fungi and bacteria and increase viral resistance in tobacco plants.

Protein interactions

The molecular mechanisms in plants are complex, as are the plant responses to pathogens. This plant response involves a large number of interactions initiated by an increase in hormones that trigger the activation of resistance genes in plants, thereby increasing plant immunity. Pathogenic interactions with plants involve complex biological pathways followed by interactions between molecules from plants and pathogens, be it proteins with DNA, proteins, or protein interactions with other substances to form complexes to undergo their biological processes (*ligands*). Protein interactions with other molecules occur in all cellular activities, including in the process of DNA replication, transcription, translation, *splicing*, secretion, cell cycle control, signaling systems and metabolic processes.

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In the mechanism of plant immunity, especially in key SAR regulators, there are two sustainable protein interaction domains, namely Ankyrin and BTB / POZ domains. Eulgem and Somssich (2007), stated that the WRKY transcription factor complex group binding has an important role in the induction of plant resistance (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Mechanism of plant resistance through the WRKY pathway (Eulgem and Somssich, 2007)

Wang *et al.* (2005) stated the role of NPR1 in stimulating transcription through its interaction with the transcription factor TGA-bZIP. Some resistance-related interactions involve a number of chain reactions in which the expression of resistance genes is related to one another, where the activity of a gene is influenced by the activity of other genes to form complex interactions. For example, the molecule AtWRKY70 is required for both basal defense pathways and plant resistance which depend on the R gene in defense against infection with the oomycetes *Hyaloperonospora parasitica* (Knoth *et al.*, 2007). The interaction between plant resistance genes (R genes) and virulence proteins (Avr) from pathogens can even cause plants to experience cell death (apoptosis) programs (Greenberg and Yao, 2004). Research recently conducted by Candra *et al.*, 2019 successfully confirmed the interaction between Protein Replicase (Rep) and the core promoter of NPR1 in several domains.

There are several methods that can be used to analyze the interactions between proteins and nucleic acids. *In vitro* analysis can use techniques *footprinting assay* (Galas and Schmitz, 1978), *electrophoretic mobility shift assay* (EMSA), *southwestern blotting* (Bowen *et al.*, 1980), *yeast one-hybrid assay* (Y2H) (Joung *et al.*, 2000), *phage display* (Choo and Klug, 1994) and *proximity ligation assay* (Gustafsdottir *et al.*, 2007). *In vivo* Versatile techniques such as *Chromatin Immunoprecipitation* (ChIP) and its variants, *DNA identification Adenine Transferase* and *3C* and *ChipLoop* assays can also be applied (Nelson *et al.*, 2006; Simonis *et al.*, 2007). *In silico* analysis is also required to provide a computational basis for determining protein-DNA interactions. Biophysical techniques such as the technique *Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer* (FRET), *FRET-FLIM*, *Circular Dichroism*, *Atomic Force Microscopy*, *Nuclear Magnetic Resonance* (NMR) and *Surface Plasmon Resonance* (SPR) can also be applied (Dey *et al.*, 2012).

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In the case of infection *Geminivirus*, gemini virus mRNA will interact with several proteins originating from the *host*. This interaction will affect the biological processes that occur in the *host*, such as affecting the function of plasmodesmata, *silencing*, cell differentiation processes, gene expression, influencing the cell cycle, DNA replication and cell proliferation processes. This interaction will have an impact on several processes, including a decrease in the transcription function of mRNA by viral proteins (mRNAs *transcriptional down-regulation*), the occurrence of post-transcriptional modification (*Post-Transcriptional Modification*) through a release process *decapping* so that the mRNA will be degraded, and obstructing the translation process with or without truncation of mRNA (Herbert and Nag, 2016).

Protein Interactions *In vitro* (Electrophoretic Mobility Shift Assay(EMSA) and Bioinformatics

Analysis of protein interactions using *EMSA* is not a new approach. This method was introduced in 1995 by Levy *et al.* (1995) in examining the transcription regulation of genes controlling growth *endothelial vascular* in mice. *EMSA* is a very fast and sensitive method for detecting interactions that occur between proteins and nucleotides (Hellman and Fried, 2007). In addition, in its technical application, the use of *EMSA* in protein analysis is very easy. The movement of DNA that interacts with proteins is much slower than that of non-interacting DNA. So when visualized, the DNA bands that interact with the protein will be far above the control DNA bands or the non-interacting DNA bands (Figure 3). The movement of proteins that do *binding* with nucleotides will move slower (B) when compared to proteins that do not interact with nucleotides (F), it can be seen in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. EMSA visualization results. Source (Hellman and Fried, 2007).

Apart from *in vitro*, protein analysis with other molecules (DNA, Ligand, protein) can also be done *in silico*, using several *software*. *The software* is used to predict the occurrence of interactions and the position of these interactions on the protein or DNA being tested. In this analysis, complete information is needed about the molecules we are testing so that the analysis program can be carried out precisely and predictions of the interactions that occur are more precise and accurate. This information is related to the DNA / Protein characteristics to be analyzed.

analysis, *In silico* among others, can be done using *software Computes Atlas of Surface Topography of Protein (CASTp)* (<http://sts.Bioe.uic.edu/castp/index.html?3trg>). Laskowski *et al.*, (1996) stated that *CASTp* is a *web server* that can be used to comprehensively analyze protein characteristics and can also be used to determine the interacting protein side. It has a platform *online* that can be used to determine the position, visualization and calculation of interaction positions in the 3D protein structure computationally based on geometry and algorithms (Binkowski *et al.*, 2003). *The software* can also provide comprehensive and detailed quantitative characterization on the surface of proteins which are usually convex and are areas that frequently interact with other molecules (Laskowski *et al.*, 1996).

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software Anotheris Swissdock (<http://www.swissdock.ch>) which can be used to determine protein interactions with small molecules. programs Docking have a wide range of applications which are generally used in protein engineering. For example, interactions between proteins and other molecules can pave the way for mutating certain amino acids which can increase or inhibit interactions (Grosdidier *et al.*, 2011). Regarding Efficiency and advantages software, Swissdock is a development of a number of software docking includes Docking server (<http://www.dockingserver.com/web>), DockingAtUTMB (<http://docking.utmb.edu/>), Pardock (<http://www.scfbio-iitd.res.in/dock/pardock.jsp>), PatchDock (<http://bioinfo3d.cs.tau.ac.il/PatchDock/>) and others. So that Swissdock is a software that can analyze completely and comprehensively (Grosdidier *et al.*, 2011)

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